

Factors influencing African Youths at Higher Education Institutions to Shop Online: A Study of Uganda

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ABSTRACT

Online shopping is the current dotcom era for businesses to achieve a competitive edge. The emergence of Smartphones and relative improvements in the Information and Technology (IT) infrastructures among other factors, have triggered youths in developing countries to shop online. Various studies have shown reasons for people to shop online but less has been researched about the youths' intention to shop online at higher education institutions of learning, such as Makerere University Business School (MUBS). Hence, to bridge the knowledge gap, this study aimed at examining factors influencing African Youths at higher education institutions to shop online, in the context of MUBS in Uganda. Questionnaires were distributed among the youths via online survey. The quantitative data was collected from 71 respondents and analyzed using PLS-SEM assisted with SmartPLS 3. The findings revealed that there is a significant relationship between hedonic and satisfaction among youths shopping line ($p = 0.00$), and there was also a significant relationship between subjective norms and satisfaction among youths shopping line ($p = 0.02$). The results show that key factors which trigger the youths' intention to satisfactorily shop online in Uganda's higher education institution are hedonic and subjective norms.

Keyword: African Youths, online shopping, higher education institutions

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1. INTRODUCTION

Shopping procedure has been changed due to the rapid growth of internet and this has narrowed the digital divide globally. When customers shop online, they are assured of some paybacks in line with the information search stage of shopping (Rose and Samouel, 2009) and the act of purchase. Cheung *et al.* (2005) established factors influencing consumer purchase behaviour online, both internally and externally. Davenport *et al.* (2012) identify “reward sensitivity” as an influence upon compulsive buying proposing that an individual who is highly sensitive to rewards will respond to enjoyable stimuli such as food or shopping. Hedonic motivations have been identified in relation to online shopping by various scholars (Childers *et al.*, 2001; Arnold and Reynolds, 2003; Kim and Eastin, 2011; Martinez-Lopez, Pla-Garcia, Gazquez-Abad and Rodriguez-Ardura, 2016). For instance, Martinez *et al.* (2016) investigated hedonic motives for online consumer behaviour and found that hedonic aspects of online consumption include visual appeal, intrinsic enjoyment and socialize. Literature reveals that positive feelings of pleasure or excitement are concomitant with compulsive buying (Lejoyeux and Weinstein, 2010).

Most studies suggest that convenience is the most common factor that motivates consumers to shop online through the internet which is in line with (Chen and Chang, 2003; Fenech and O’Cass, 2001; Jarvenpaa and Todd, 1997; Karayanni, 2003; Minjoon *et al.*, 2004; McKinney, 2004). Perceived usefulness of online shopping means that the user’s beliefs about whether he or she, when shopping on line, can search for and compare products, get information and a lower price, and thus gain more from the transaction (Broekhuizen and Huisingsh, 2007). Online shopping as a technology can also be exposed to experience such as level of satisfaction emanating from consumers purchase intent. A similar study by Njoroge *et al.* (2012) did study on identifying facets of technology satisfaction and found that satisfaction is a key factor in measuring consumers purchase intent.

Chang *et al.* (2005) recognized different determinants of e-shopping behavior for consumers which mainly covered three indispensable elements. Namely: characteristics of e-shopping as a shopping channel, consumer characteristics, and vendor and product characteristics. It is suggested that the former two have been examined extensively in previous research. It is vital in supplementing to literature on behavior factors of e-shoppers since their intention and actual use vary from one product to another as well as countries. Similarly, Alsoud and Othman (2018) highlighted the need for more studies on online shopping. Therefore, in order to fill the knowledge gap, the main aim of this study was to examine factors that influence African youths at higher education institution to shop online in the context of Uganda. The objectives of this study are to establish the relationship between hedonic and satisfaction among youths shopping online, and the relationship between subjective norms and satisfaction among youths shopping online.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Definition of Key Concepts

2.1.1 Online shopping

Online shopping is considered convenient and allows for easy price comparisons (Chiang and Dholakia, 2003). Online shopping is defined as the process customers go through to purchase products or services over the internet (Abdeldayem, 2010). Online shopping is described as a process where the customer purchases products and services directly from the seller using the internet as a medium (Rizwan *et al.*, 2014). Example of online shopping is by using websites known as web shops like Amazon.com (Abdeldayem, 2010). This study adopts definition online shopping by Abdeldayem (2010). In addition, the African Youths in this study are the African male and female below the age of 36 years and above 18 years (students and staff of MUBS) and were meant to be actively shopping online using the various online shops.

2.1.2 Hedonic

Hedonic serves as emotion regulation function, predict reduced negative affect, carefreeness, vitality and life satisfaction (Henderson, Knight and Richardson, 2012). The concept of hedonic is associated with shopping motivation and thus several scholars, such as Kim and Eastin (2011) have defined hedonic shopping motivation as the enjoyment of shopping for its own sake, the pursuit fun, novelty and excitement while shopping. Huta and Waltermann (2014) describe hedonic motivation as seeking pleasure and avoiding pain. This paper defines hedonic as shopping experience exhibiting aspects of excitement, escape from boredom and enjoyment.

2.1.3 Subjective Norms

Subjective norms are referred to as the perceived social pressure to perform or not perform the behaviour (Pavlov and Chai, 2002). Subjective norms constitute societal norm and social influence (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975). Other scholars have defined subjective norms as the belief of an important person or group of people will approve and support a particular behaviour (Ham *et al.*, 2015). Furthermore, subjective norms are determined by perceived social pressure from others for an individual to behave in a certain manner and motivation to comply with those people's views (Ham *et al.*, 2015). The definition of subjective norms in this paper is adopted from Fishbein and Ajzen (1975).

2.1.4 Intent to Shop Online

To shop online is an innovative form of trade that takes place on the internet where customers purchase products and services directly from the seller (Rizwan *et al.*, 2015). Individuals intend to shop online because it saves time (Rizwan *et al.*, 2015). Previous scholars have identified shopping intention as a substitute for purchase behavior which also needs to be explored (Lim *et al.*, 2016). Intentions are considered as an indicator of the extent that people are willing to approach certain behaviour and how many attempts they are trying so as to perform certain behaviour (Ajzen, 1991). Kim *et al.* (2008) indicated that intention to purchase online is based on the relationship between behavioural intention and actual behavior. This paper refers to intent to shop online as the purchase of buy products or services online which is associated with satisfaction.

2.2 Theoretical Framework and Hypothesis Development

The theory of Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) was developed by Davis *et al.* (1989). The theory of technology acceptance model assumes that an individual behaviour intention to use a system is determined by beliefs in terms of usefulness and ease of use (Venkatesh, Davis and Walton, 2000). Alsoud and Othman (2018) have used the technology acceptance model to provide empirical understanding of Jordanian consumers towards online shopping and found that website in terms of quality, credibility and security protection were significantly related to customers' online shopping intention. Other scholars have also used technology acceptance model such as Aineah (2016) and Monsuwe *et al.* (2004).

The study by Monsuwe *et al.* (2004) applied technology of acceptance model and argued that hedonic orientation of online shopping reflects enjoyment aspect since hedonists seek plus enjoyable experiences, fun and fantasy. It further states that, within technology acceptance model, hedonic orientation appears to influence consumer attitude toward online shopping. In addition, Aineah (2016) focused on the factors affecting the online purchase intent of the college students using technology acceptance model with the extended constructs of trust, enjoyment and e-quality. The study by DeLone and McLean (2003) mentioned that user satisfaction is closely interrelated with intention to purchase online website. Aldhmour and Sarayrah (2016) used technology acceptance model to investigate factors influencing consumer's intention to use online shopping and found that subjective norms had positive direct impact on consumer's attitude while other perceived of ease of use, perceived usefulness and perceived risk did not have a direct impact on customers' intention.

For subjective norms, the study by Aldhmour and Sarayah (2016) used the Theory of Reason Action (TRA) developed in 1975 by Fishbein and Ajzen suggests that a person's behavior is determined by intention, attitude and subjective norms (Silverman *et al.*, 2016). These studies show that the theory of technology acceptance model along with the theory of reason action have been used to examine online shopping. This study also adopts the theory of technology acceptance model and theory of reasoned action to examine factors that influence youths at higher education institution to shop online. In analyzing the youths' intention to shop online, this study theorizes that there is a significant relationship between hedonic and intention to shop online, and the relationship subjective norms and intention to shop online.

2.3 Empirical Literature Review

Abdeldayem (2010) examined online shopping by studying customer satisfaction with online shopping. Abdeldayem (2010) conducted the quantitative survey of university students in Dubai and findings revealed that attitudes toward online shopping and intention to shop online were affected by ease of use, enjoyment and perceived web-store traits, channel traits and consumer traits. In Malaysia, a study by Yuliharsi, Islam and Daudi (2011) investigated factors influencing student's buying intention through internet shopping in an institution of higher learning. The study used convenience sampling to obtain 300 respondents. The study found that the factors influencing student's buying intention the internet shopping were usefulness, ease of use, security and compatibility.

Other factors influencing online shopping intention were revealed by Alsoud and Othman (2018). The study by Alsoud and Othman (2018) was carried in Jordan and used Partial Least Square (PLS) analysis to test the factors that enhance Jordanian academic-staff intention to purchase online. The findings from a sample of respondents which were mainly male (62%) with majority aged 30 to 39 years (88%) indicated that factors such as website quality, website credibility and security protection significantly relates to online shopping intention.

On the other hand, Njoroge *et al.* (2012) identified facets of technology satisfaction measure development and application with findings that differences manifest on how satisfied students are with technology which is mainly from four factors which are proficiency, assessment, performance and preference towards web-courses. Although satisfaction was used in the study, the focus was on course material as opposed to shopping online. Shopping online is a technology and studied with guidance from the theory of technology acceptance model. In addition, the study by Saleem *et al.* (2015) indicated that satisfaction is one of the important factors which impact purchase intention. This study adopts satisfaction as a measure of youths' intention to shop online.

Martinez-Lopez *et al.* (2016) conducted a qualitative and quantitative study in Spain with participants from University schools as respondents to invest hedonic motives for online consumption experience by applying exploratory factor analysis and confirmatory factor analysis. The study concluded that measurement for hedonic motives for online consumption were visual appeal, enduring involvement with a product or service, sensation seeking, escape, intrinsic enjoyment, hang out, social shopping, self expression and role shopping.

A study conducted in Kenya on online shopping found that some of the factors affecting online purchase intent of college students were perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use and transactional security (Aineah, 2016). There are still limited studies on the concept of shopping in Africa. Few studies have done research on shopping and focused on convenience shopping for industrial products related to traditional methods of shopping (Mkwizu *et al.*, 2018; Wilbard *et al.*, 2018). However, these studies have advocated on the need to research more on shopping. Furthermore, Alsoud and Othman (2018) also noted that there are limited studies on online shopping. Therefore, this paper fills the knowledge gap by examining factors that influence youths at higher education institution to shop online.

3. METHODOLOGY

The study's geographical scope was Uganda. Quantitative research method was used in this study to examine the factors influencing youths' online shopping. Students from Makerere University Business School (MUBS) in Kampala, Uganda were distributed with semi structured questionnaires using online survey. In this paper, the independent variables are hedonic and subjective norms while the dependent variable is intent to shop online were adopted and customized from previous studies. The items measuring hedonic which were adopted and customized from Martinez-Lopez *et al.* (2016). The statements that measured hedonic were: Online shopping is more exciting than conventional shopping (Hedo1), Online shopping is boring compared to traditional shopping (Hedo2); Online shopping is more enjoyable than offline (Hedo3).

The items to measure subjective norms were adopted and customized from the study by Lin (2007), and Zarrad and Debabi (2012). The statements for subjective norms were: People who are important to me would think that I should shop online (Nosov1); People who influence me would think that I should shop online (Norsov2); People whose opinions are valued to me would prefer that I shop online (Norsov3); Online shopping offers opportunity to exchange information with other online shoppers (Norsov4); Online shopping provides platform to share experiences with other online shoppers (Norsov5); Online shopping extend my personal relationships (Norsov6). The items for measuring satisfaction were adopted and customized from Njoroge *et al.* (2012). The statements for satisfaction were: Overall, I am happy with my online shopping experience (Sat1); Overall, I am satisfied with the benefits I obtain from online shopping (Sat2); If I need to buy certain products, I am more likely to purchase them online (Sat3); I am likely to increase my online purchase in the future (Sat4).

The data was collected from a sample size of 71 MUBS students using convenience sampling. The composite reliability values were reliable and indicated hedonic was 0.73, subjective norms was 0.86 and for satisfaction was 0.90. The collected data was analysed using descriptive statistics using SPSS version 20 and PLS-SEM assisted with SmartPLS 3.

4. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The characteristics of the sampled respondents are shown in Table 1. Findings indicate that most of the respondents were females (52.1%), between 21 to 35 years old aged (100%), product shopped were electronics (64.8%) and number of years of using online shopping was 1 to 2 years (38.0%). The results imply that many of the respondents were young females who shopped electronics products for a period of 1 to 2 years. These results differ from Alsoud and Othman (2018) who found mostly males aged 30 to 39 years. These results vary because males and females in different locations have different uses of online shopping.

Table 1: Respondents Characteristics (n=71)

		Frequencies	Uganda
Age Groups	21-35	71	100.0%
Gender	Male	34	47.9%
	Female	37	52.1%
Product Shopped	Clothing	10	14.1%
	Electronics	46	64.8%
	Food and Drinks	15	21.1%
No. of Years of online shopping	Less than a year	14	19.7%
	1 to 2 years	27	38.0%
	3 to 5 years	23	32.4%
	More than 5 years	7	9.9%

Source: Field data (2019)

Other items were dropped due to low loadings. The collinearity values for the retained items which are hedonic2 (1.037), hedonic3 (1.037), subjective norms as Norsov1(1.942), Norsov2

(2.546), Norsov3 (3.665), Norsov4 (3.1), Norosov6 (1.766), Satisfaction as Sat1 (1.391), Sat2 (4.606) and Sat3 (4.782) indicated Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) < 4 or (VIF) < 5 and this is acceptable according to Hair, Black, Babin and Anderson (2010) and Ringle, Wende and Becker (2015) respectively.

Using bootstrapping technique, the PLS-SEM analysis revealed findings in Table 2; there is a significant relationship between hedonic and satisfaction for youths online shopping ($p=0.00$). This further shows that the relationship between hedonic and satisfaction is significant ($p=0.000$). The results in Table 3 indicate that there is a significant relationship between subjective norms and satisfaction for youths online shopping ($p=0.02$). These results suggest that hedonic and subjective norms are factors influencing youths to shop online. Significant results support technology acceptance model and theory of reasoned action whereby the youths online shopping is influenced by hedonic and subjective norms in the context of Uganda's higher education institutions. The results of this study are in line with the study by Aldmour and Sarayah (2016) which found that subjective norms significantly influenced intentions to shop online. On the other hand, results of this study vary from Martinez-Lopez *et al.* (2016) which did not have excitement as a measurement of hedonic while in this study showed excitement as an aspect of hedonic relates to intention to shop online in terms of satisfaction.

5. CONCLUSION

This study concludes that hedonic and subjective norms are factors influencing youths at higher education institutions to shop online in Uganda. The results of this study have implications theoretically and practically to online shop companies, website developers, internet service providers, policy makers, youths and future researchers. The theoretical implication is that the application of technology acceptance model and theory of reasoned action can guide the analysis of factors influencing youths at higher education to shop online in the context of Uganda due to the significant results of hedonic and subjective norms in relation to intention to shop online. From the practical point of view, more online shops should be set up to increase competition which will increase online shopping hedonic aspects, such as excitement and enjoyment when shopping online. Those online shopping platforms already in the Ugandan market should aspire to be on the creative edge in order to continue being useful to the online users and specifically youths at MUBS; online shops should be user friendly; shopping sites should not ask for excessive information from the customers since it erodes the users privacy due to lack of trust hence resulting to a decrease in the shopping process; the government should have policies that look into protecting end users as they use online shopping platforms. For the academia, these findings will help to improve the literature and future research on online shopping.

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